

INTELLIGENT MONITORING SYSTEM FOR NICU (NEONATA INTENSIVE CARE UNIT)

N. Chiranjeevi¹, Narike Vishnu²,

Gade Rohith³, Ms. Md. Yasmeen⁴

^{1,2,3} UG Student, Dept. of ECE, CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

⁴ Assistant Professor, Dept. of ECE,

CMR Institute of Technology, Hyderabad

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the project is to develop an Intelligent Neonatal Monitoring System based on temperature and pulse rate data. In the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), there are premature babies and other ill babies who need extra care from the doctors, nurses as well as medical supplies. Therefore, an intelligent neonatal monitoring system should be a good solution in order to help them to observe neonates frequently and consistently. This system transmits the vital signs of the neonate such as body temperature and pulse rate to the Internet of Things (IoT) called ThingSpeak. The body temperature and the pulse rate will be detected by LM35 temperature sensor and pulse sensor respectively. These information will be sent to the IoT via ESP8266 Wi-Fi Shield. IoT helps the doctors and nurses to be connected with the neonate's vital signs and it is helpful in monitoring the neonates at anytime and anywhere through the internet. The

percentage difference between LM35 temperature sensor and digital thermometer is less than 3% while the pulse rate can be varied according to the physical activity. This develops system will providing efficiency and reliability which will play a vital role for better care.

INTRODUCTION

In the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), there are premature babies and other ill babies who need extra care from the doctors, nurses as well as medical supplies. World Health Organization (WHO) defines neonate as a newborn baby who is 28 days of life [1]. At this critical age, they have a high possibility of death due to many complication. Sudden Infant Death Syndrome (SIDS) and apnea are the incidents might happen to them. SIDS is the sudden and unexplained death of an infant under 1 year of age [2]. Sometimes, babies are born with problems in the part of their brain that controls breathing, pulse rate, blood pressure,

temperature, and waking from sleep [3]. Therefore, they need close and direct supervision from the doctors and nurses. Babies who need special cares will be admitted into NICU for close supervising and monitoring by pediatric doctors and nurses. In a few situations, it becomes difficult for them to monitor the neonates because they need to be presented near the neonates all the time. They need to check the neonate's condition such as temperature and pulse rate frequently and consistently. Fig. 1 shows the neonatal care environment in the NICU. All the sensors are connected by wires to a monitoring unit outside of the incubator. The display next to the incubator visualizes the vital sign signals and sensor's reading from these sensors used in NICU (Fig. 2). The health information in the NICU are collected and recorded with continuous monitoring. The monitor will updates at regular time intervals and provides a real-time monitoring system. In NICU, the continuous health monitoring is important to keep a neonate survive and alive with many specialized types of equipment provided [4]. Continuous monitoring these neonates also plays an important role to improve the health condition and reduce the number of newborn death. The parents are vulnerable during the infant's hospitalization in NICU because of

their emotional stress can affect the infants [5]. Any abnormalities in the health parameters can be directly notified and are informed to the doctor or duty nurses. Developing various health monitoring systems have vast improvement in health sector especially for neonatal monitoring system. Many research and studies relating to the implementation of various sensors which has been used in order to increase the efficiency and accuracy of the health monitoring system [6][7]. Based on the comparison, each of the monitoring system has its own advantages and disadvantages. Few researches used GSM modem and Bluetooth module to send and receive the data for the monitoring of vital parameter of neonates through SMS. The analysis, collection and dissemination of health data and information from the NICU monitors were designed to improve the survival of the neonate. From these vital signs information, it can identify the existence of medical problem because each neonate has different condition. Therefore, continuous monitoring system should be developed as a good solution in order to help them to observe the tiny neonate frequently. With the state-of-the-art mobile application, the system gets to be more intelligent and smarter. Hence, smartphone can be a platform and medium

for doctors and nurses to create an application for neonatal monitoring system. All the vital signs can be continuously monitored wirelessly through Internet of Things technology.

LITERATURE SURVEY

- **A.-M. A. Ramos et al., “Preterm birth: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunisation safety data,” *Vaccine*, vol. 34, no. 49, pp. 6047– 6056, 2016.**

The aim of this study is to highlight the predictive role of perinatal fetal main pulmonary artery (MPA) Doppler measurements in neonatal respiratory distress syndrome development. Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) is one of the lead causes of neonatal respiratory distress as well as neonatal death. Thus, it seems logic to evaluate fetal lung maturity before labour. Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) implies a respiratory deterioration that presents at or shortly after birth due to a deficiency of natural phospholipid namely pulmonary surfactant, which is essential in decreasing the surface tension inside

the alveoli thus, preventing alveolar collapse. RDS is one of the main causes of neonatal morbidity and mortality [1]. **P. S. Blair, P. Sidebotham, P. J. Berry, M. Evans, and P. J. Fleming, “Major epidemiological changes in sudden infant death syndrome: A 20-year population-based study in the UK,” *Lancet*, 2006.**

Over the past 20 years, the proportion of children who died from SIDS while co-sleeping with their parents, has risen from 12% to 50% ($p < 0.0001$), but the actual number of SIDS deaths in the parental bed has halved ($p = 0.01$). The proportion seems to have increased partly because the Back to Sleep campaign led to fewer deaths in infants sleeping alone—rather than because of a rise in deaths of infants who bed-shared, and partly because of an increase in the number of deaths in infants sleeping with their parents on a sofa. The proportion of deaths in families from deprived socioeconomic backgrounds has risen from 47% to 74% ($p = 0.003$), the prevalence of maternal smoking during pregnancy from 57% to 86% ($p = 0.0004$), and the

proportion of pre-term infants from 12% to 34% ($p=0.0001$). Although many SIDS infants come from large families, first-born infants are now the largest group. The age of infants who bed-share is significantly smaller than that before the campaign, and fewer are breastfed. **H. F. Krous, “Sudden Infant Death Syndrome and Unclassified Sudden Infant Deaths: A Definitional and Diagnostic Approach,” Pediatrics, 2004.**

The definition of sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) originally appeared in 1969 and was modified 2 decades later. During the following 15 years, an enormous amount of additional information has emerged, justifying additional refinement of the definition of SIDS to incorporate epidemiologic features, risk factors, pathologic features, and ancillary test findings. An expert panel of pediatric and forensic pathologists and pediatricians considered these issues and developed a new general definition of SIDS for administrative and vital statistics purposes. The new definition was then stratified to facilitate research into sudden infant

death. Another category, defined as unclassified sudden infant deaths, was introduced for cases that do not meet the criteria for a diagnosis of SIDS and for which alternative diagnoses of natural or unnatural conditions were equivocal. **L. Suresh, N. A. Latha, B. R. Murthy, K. T. Alam, and K. Jyothi, “Neonatal Monitoring System,” Int. J. Eng. Res. Appl., vol. 4, no. 7, pp. 12–15, 2014**

Kangaroo mother care is an apparatus that provides closed and controlled environmental for the preterm babies. A Preterm birth is commonly defined as any birth base 37 weeks completed weeks of gestation period. This paper deals with cost effective design of incubator that monitors parameters like pulse rate, temperature, humidity, child security and the readings will be continuously displayed In the LED screen and also monitoring the details to the corresponding doctor, nurse and parents by using GSM. The power failure problem is also eliminated by using solar panel. We also intimate the parents about feeding time, dressing time, ear check, eye check. But many of the

existing system does not mentioned about above problem and have adopted only with humidity and temperature and also by manual control. So the main objective of this research is to overcome drawbacks and provide eco friendly service to all common people.

- **G. Watson, “Parental liminality: A way of understanding the early experiences of parents who have a very preterm infant,” J. Clin. Nurs., 2011.**

Globally, 11.1% of births are born preterm (before 37 weeks of gestation)¹ whereas 14% in Nepal.² As born immature, they are vulnerable to morbidities and mortality. Therefore they require hospitalization for a significant period in neonatal care units (NCUs).³ Retrospective study done in 2011 in TUTH indicated hospitalization of (45%) of infants born preterm.⁴ Preterm birth and hospitalization are stressful for mothers and family.^{5,6} They experience emotions like fear, anxiety, uncertainty, distress and loneliness. Because of early and prolonged separation, and special

care needs of the infant, these mothers feel powerlessness and lose their confidence for maternal roles. ^{7,8} Enabling maternal role with care and support is essential to ensure proper care of newborn after NCU stay.⁹ Understanding their experience is essential to plan effective care and support to them. ¹⁰ The information is limited in the context of Nepal. Therefore, this study was conducted to find out the experience of mothers having preterm newborns in NCUs

EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing systems for monitoring neonates in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) generally incorporate a combination of traditional monitoring devices and electronic health record (EHR) systems. These systems typically include vital signs monitors, pulse oximeters, and temperature control devices to track the newborn's physiological parameters. Vital signs, such as heart rate, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation, are continuously monitored to detect any deviations from normal ranges. Most NICUs rely on nurse observation and periodic checks of monitoring devices to assess the baby's condition. Electronic health records store and organize patient information, including vital

signs, medications, and medical history, providing a centralized repository for healthcare providers to access critical data. While existing systems offer valuable insights, they may face limitations in real-time analysis and proactive alerts for early intervention. The integration of artificial intelligence and advanced analytics to predict potential health issues and trigger timely alerts is an area where ongoing research and development are taking place. Furthermore, parental involvement is often facilitated through periodic updates by healthcare providers or direct communication. The existing systems may not have dedicated interfaces for parents to actively monitor their baby's condition in real-time. In terms of environmental monitoring, NICUs commonly implement measures to maintain optimal conditions, including temperature and humidity control, but these might not be integrated into a comprehensive monitoring system. Additionally, infection control measures are enforced through standard protocols, but there may be room for improvement in leveraging advanced technologies for real-time monitoring. While existing NICU systems provide effective monitoring and care, the continuous advancements in sensor technologies, artificial intelligence, and data analytics

present opportunities to enhance the precision, immediacy, and proactive nature of neonatal care, creating a more comprehensive and intelligent monitoring system.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed intelligent monitoring system for the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) aims to revolutionize neonatal care by incorporating state-of-the-art technologies and advanced features. The system introduces a network of non-invasive smart sensors to monitor vital signs, including heart rate, respiratory rate, blood oxygen levels, and temperature, in real-time. Leveraging artificial intelligence algorithms, the system analyzes continuous streams of data, providing healthcare professionals with predictive insights and early warnings in the event of abnormalities, thus facilitating timely intervention. To enhance remote monitoring, the proposed system includes a mobile application that enables healthcare providers to monitor NICU patients from a distance. The system ensures seamless integration with the hospital's Electronic Health Records (EHR), allowing for a comprehensive and centralized view of a newborn's medical history and current condition. Environmental monitoring is

advanced through the deployment of temperature and humidity sensors, maintaining optimal conditions within the NICU and contributing to infection control. The system prioritizes parental involvement with a user-friendly interface, providing real-time updates and secure communication channels between healthcare providers and parents. A comprehensive data visualization dashboard offers healthcare professionals customizable views of vital signs, historical trends, and alerts, facilitating informed decision-making. The proposed system is designed with scalability and flexibility in mind, accommodating an increasing number of neonates and evolving medical practices. The modular design ensures compatibility with existing NICU infrastructure and medical equipment.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

HARDWARE COMPONENTS

LCD (Liquid Cristal Display)

Introduction:

A liquid crystal display (LCD) is a thin, flat display device made up of any number of color or monochrome pixels arrayed in front of a light source or reflector. Each pixel consists of a column of liquid crystal molecules suspended between two transparent electrodes, and two polarizing filters, the axes of polarity of which are perpendicular to each other. Without the liquid crystals between them, light passing through one would be blocked by the other. The liquid crystal twists the polarization of light entering one filter to allow it to pass through the other.

A program must interact with the outside world using input and output devices that communicate directly with a human being. One of the most common devices attached to an controller is an LCD display. Some of the most common LCDs connected to the contollers are 16X1, 16x2 and 20x2 displays. This means 16 characters per line by 1 line 16 characters per line by 2 lines and 20 characters per line by 2 lines, respectively.

DHT TEMPERATURE & HUMIDITY SENSORS.

These sensors are very basic and slow, but are great for hobbyists who want to do some basic data logging. The DHT sensors are made of two parts, a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor. There is also a very basic chip inside that does some analog to digital conversion and spits out a digital signal with the temperature and humidity. The digital signal is fairly easy to read using any microcontroller.

Humidity is the measure of water vapour present in the air. The level of humidity in air affects various physical, chemical and biological processes. In industrial applications, humidity can affect the business cost of the products, health and safety of the employees. So, in semiconductor industries and control system industries measurement of humidity is very important. Humidity measurement determines the amount of moisture present in the gas that can be a mixture of water vapour, nitrogen, argon or pure gas etc... Humidity sensors are of two types based on their measurement units. They are a relative humidity sensor and Absolute humidity sensor. DHT11 is a digital temperature and humidity sensor.

What is a DHT11 Sensor?

DHT11 is a low-cost digital sensor for sensing temperature and humidity. This sensor can be easily interfaced with any

micro-controller such as Arduino, Raspberry Pi etc... to measure humidity and temperature instantaneously.

DHT11 humidity and temperature sensor is available as a sensor and as a module. The difference between this sensor and module is the pull-up resistor and a power-on LED. DHT11 is a relative humidity sensor. To measure the surrounding air this sensor uses a [thermistor](#) and a capacitive humidity sensor.

Working Principle of DHT11 Sensor

DHT11 sensor consists of a capacitive humidity sensing element and a thermistor for sensing temperature. The humidity sensing [capacitor](#) has two electrodes with a moisture holding substrate as a dielectric between them. Change in the capacitance value occurs with the change in humidity levels. The IC measure, process this changed resistance values and change them into digital form.

For measuring temperature this sensor uses a Negative Temperature coefficient thermistor, which causes a decrease in its resistance value with increase in temperature. To get larger resistance value even for the smallest change in temperature, this sensor is usually

made up of semiconductor ceramics or polymers.

The temperature range of DHT11 is from 0 to 50 degree Celsius with a 2-degree accuracy. Humidity range of this sensor is from 20 to 80% with 5% accuracy. The sampling rate of this sensor is 1Hz .i.e. it gives one reading for every second. DHT11 is small in size with operating voltage from 3 to 5 volts. The maximum current used while measuring is 2.5mA.

DHT11 Sensor

DHT11 sensor has four pins- VCC, GND, Data Pin and a not connected pin. A pull-up resistor of 5k to 10k ohms is provided for communication between sensor and micro-controller.

BUZZERS

In common parlance a Buzzer is a signaling device that is not a loudspeaker. It can be mechanical, electromechanical, or electronic

(a piezo transducer). BeStar produces Buzzers in every available configuration for a wide variety of applications. A Piezo transducer can produce the sound for panel mount buzzers, household goods, medical devices and even very loud sirens. When a lower frequency is required an electromagnetic buzzer can fill the need. These are very common in automotive chimes and higher end clinical diagnostic devices. The BeStar buzzer range includes self drive units with their own drive circuitry (indicators), or external drive units, which allow the designer the flexibility to create their own sound patterns.

BeStar buzzers, whether a piezo buzzer, or an electro-magnetic buzzer, self (indicator) or non-self (transducer) drive are available with a variety of mounting methods, such as surface mount, thru hole, flange, wire leads or panel mounting. Sealed, high temp, very loud, weather resistant; whatever your application requirement is, BeStar has a piezo buzzer that will meet your design criteria.

CONCLUSION

This project can offer an intelligent neonatal monitoring system using multi-sensors based on Android application. The body temperature and pulse rate of the neonate were able to detect by using LM35

temperature sensor and pulse sensor, respectively. This system will greatly help the nurses or doctors to monitor the neonate closely and continuously analyze the neonate's vital signs. Moreover, the system is capable in retrieving a real-time data of temperature and pulse rate from the IoT cloud, ThingSpeak directly to the user's mobile phone. This developed system will provide efficiency and reliability which will play a vital role for better care in patient management.

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